

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ISSUES IN ASSIMILATING TECHNICAL TERMS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

The process of learning a language is infinite. Students have different attitudes towards embracing new knowledge, enlarging vocabulary, practicing skills, and using the right strategies when it comes to facing challenges and dealing with issues they encounter in assimilating new technical and specific terms.

Thus, when the teachers know the strengths and weaknesses of their students, the process of assimilating the new terms is facilitated. For this reason, an open-ended questionnaire was given to first year engineering students about the issue that they encounter in learning ESP (English for Specific Purposes) terms. Then, a survey was conducted on more students to find out the aspects of word usage that they consider as the main barrier that makes it difficult for them to assimilate the terms fast and properly.

Four main alternatives were given to them to find out the main issue, and suggestions are given to help teachers and students facilitate the process of assimilating the new ESP terms at best.

Keywords: technical terms, issue, students, strategy, challenge, assimilate

Literature Review

From the very start, difficulty has been explained in linguistic terms, and by controlling the difficulty of linguistic input to learners, levels of difficulty can be specified. (Nunan, 1992).

Progress refers to general growth not focused on a specific task. It serves as a long-term goal and tends to facilitate the growth of educators' perspective of teaching and of themselves as educators.

Richards and Farrel (2005) listed some examples of goals from a performance perspective:

- To understand how the process of second language development occurs.
- To understand how our roles change in relation to the type of students we are teaching.
- To understand the types of decision-making that arise during the learning process.
- To review the theories and principles of language teaching.
- To develop an understanding of different teaching styles.
- To determine students' perceptions of classroom activities.

Professional progress must go beyond personal and individual reflection.

Unlike teaching English as a foreign language or as a second language, there is a mismatch between the pedagogy and the research field, meaning that there is a gap between textbooks and pedagogical practice on the one hand and research findings on the other. Harwood (2005) states that there is a difference between how academic writers write and what textbooks teach about writing.

Robinson (1991) states that the main role that an ESP teacher should have is flexibility. For Robinson (1991), flexibility means changing from being a general English teacher to a purposeful English teacher. This flexible lecturer must deal with different groups of students, often at short notice. However, Robinson may imply that it is precisely the responsibility of the general English teacher to teach ESP classes.

For Widdowson (1998), the notion of authenticity has been the subject of controversy for several decades and there may still be researchers who may not yet agree with today's definition accepted by the majority.

Haloçi et al (2008), emphasize that creative tasks promote independence, are more challenging, and also require the participation of students to solve them.

Belcher (2016) recognized that ESP teachers are specialists who analyse needs, but they are designers of the specialized curricula at the same time.

Harding (2007) writes that the ESP educator should emphasize to their students that ESP is transferable in nature, so they will not face the reaction: "What does this have to do with my profession?"

In relation to this issue, there are several main steps that the lecturer can follow:

- Explain the objectives clearly.
- Explain that even if a document or activity is not from the students' particular field of study, it contains language structures, vocabulary and language approaches that can be transferred to their field of study in the same way.
- In any document or material, set out the terms and language that may be transferred.
- Always make sure there is a "transfer" phase for the activities, when the content is directly related to their work situations.

Material and method

An open-ended questionnaire was conducted to a class of 22 civil engineering students who study at the Faculty of Civil Engineering, Polytechnic University of Tirana. The purpose was to collect as many opinions as possible regarding the issues that they mostly encounter when it comes to assimilating new technical terms. Students were advised to brainstorm and list randomly every difficulty related to learning technical terms.

Another survey then was conducted using the four most mentioned alternatives given by students. The survey was extended to 214 students studying at the Faculty of Civil Engineering in four fields of study, (civil engineering, geodetic engineering, hydro-technical engineering and environmental engineering) Polytechnic University of Tirana. They study ESP first year, 14 week course, and they deal with the specific textbook "Civil Engineering".

The purpose of the study was to highlight:

- Problems when it comes to learning technical terms
 - The issue students most often face:
 - a) rare usage
 - b) difficulty in translation
 - c) difficulty in pronunciation
 - d) difficulty using ESP in other contexts

Results and discussion

The question put forward to students made them brainstorm and be aware of the difficulties they encounter. By listing challenges faced, will help students find and use the right strategies to overcome the difficulties.

The list shows the most given alternatives related to difficulties encountered:

- Short time dealing with ESP (one semester only)
- The rare usage
- Difficult words to pronounce
- No Albanian equivalent
- No grammar
- Difficulty in using the words in other contexts
- Little usage of words in everyday speech
- Difficult to memorize
- Difficult to explain
- Lots of practice needed
- Short reading passages
- Specific terms not often used from one lesson to another

In order to find out which is the barrier that engineering students mostly come across when considering assimilating technical terms, the graph below is presented with the given issues (the four most common issues given by students were chosen):

Graph 1. Results for research question:

*Which is the problem you mostly encounter when learning ESP vocabulary? a) its rare usage
b) difficulty in translation
c) difficulty in pronunciation
d) difficulty using it in other contexts*

The problem that Civil Engineering students mostly encounter when learning ESP vocabulary is the difficulty they have in using the words in other contexts (48%). This stands true as they are at the first steps of their studies. Students outside school use general English, but soon enough they will realize that ESP will be used not only in classroom contexts, in supplementary materials they have to read in order to enlarge knowledge and get more information, but in their professional medium. Most students start internships or

part time jobs, even prior to finishing their studies. Students' emotional well-being is relevant to their career choice (Zhou, 2013). Students have to have a good proficiency level at general English first, so they can succeed in ESP as well.

Overcoming the problems students have is not simply a matter of learning specialist language because more often the general use of language causes the great problem. Sometimes students have problems in under-

standing specialist texts. These are not due to the technical terminology, but mostly because of poor general vocabulary.

Students have difficulty in ESP rare usage (11%), in translation (19%), in pronunciation (22%). In fact students studying at the Faculty of Civil Engineering face more difficulties in even finding the meanings or the Albanian equivalent of ESP vocabulary. This is even due to the fact that there aren't many dictionaries available. Nevertheless in cases where the Albanian equivalent is not found, images, photos, pictures must be displayed during the learning process, so that students have a long memorization of the terms and know how to associate it with the usage and other specific terms related to it.

The attitudes that foreign language teachers have towards the use of the mother tongue by students in the classroom at different levels have undergone significant changes; from a total denial to an unwilling acceptance. If students don't use Albanian language during the classes, they will practice English and pronunciation more and will be able to use the terms in other contexts too.

Brahja et al, (2023) points out that lecturers use ESP to enrich students with additional information, so students feel more self-confident when they start their career.

Conclusions

Students must be aware that a foreign language has to be used outside the classroom medium in order to assimilate the terms learned, memorize them longer, enlarge vocabulary more, and practice pronunciation.

It's a must to read and consult other supplementary materials in ESP, use the internet, watch documentaries related to their field of study, so they not only learn more about issues in their profession and how to solve them, but at the same time they see how technical terms relate to one-another, how they are presented and used in different contexts.

Visual aids shall be used as much as possible, but when it comes to cases when students find it impossible

to memorize the ESP terms, even though the definition is given, and the Albanian equivalent is not found, then visual aid usage is indispensable.

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